

MANAGEMENT OF *GRIDHRASI* IN AYURVEDA- A CASE REPORTDr. Sumayya Iqra^{1*}, Dr. Amrutha Y.², Dr. Reshma Raghunath, Dr. Swagath N.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Large number of populations suffers from chronic low back pain. The incidence is more common in elderly age groups and in women but in present days, rising incidences of low back pain in younger generation is concerning. In Ayurveda, the symptoms of chronic low back pain associated with radiating pain to lower limbs can be related to a disease called *Gridhrasi*. *Gridhrasi* is one of the *Vatavyadhi* characterized by pain in the *kati*, *prishtha*, *uru*, *janu*, *jangha* and *pada*. It is opined that, in *Gridhrasi*, the patient's gait becomes altered due to pain resembling the walk of the vulture, hence the name *Gridhrasi*. Based on the above references of symptomatology in ayurvedic literature, *Gridhrasi* can be correlated to Sciatica. Sciatica is a condition characterized by radicular pain from the low back radiating downward along the course of the sciatic nerve. This condition not only hampers the daily functioning but also reduces the quality of life in a patient. **Objective:** A 34-year-old male patient with the diagnosis of sciatica reported to OPD with complaints of pain and stiffness in the lower back since 6 months associated with radiating pain in B/L lower limbs up to thighs. The patient also had complaints of frequent bloating of the abdomen for a year. The patient was treated with Ayurvedic therapeutic interventions such as *Kati basti*, *Sthanika abhyanga & Sweda*, *Matra Basti* and *Marma* massage along with *Vata Kaphahara & Vatahara Shamana aushadhi* were prescribed. **Results:** After 1 week of treatment, there was marked relief in the symptoms in the form of reduced pain and stiffness. The above treatment protocol has shown significant results clinically in the present study.

KEYWORDS: *Gridhrasi*, Sciatica, *Vata*, Pain.

INTRODUCTION

Gridhrasi is one of the *Nanatmaja Vatavyadhi*. It is caused due to *Vatakarahara* and *vihara* causing *Vata dosha prakopa* which gets *sthanasamshraya* in regions like *Kati*, *sphik* and *adhoshaka* resulting in *Stambha*, *ruja*, *toda* and *spandana* in these regions resulting in *Gridhrasi*.^[1] *Dhatu kshaya & Avarana* are the two main causative factors for *vatavyadhi*.^[2] In contemporary science, the disease Sciatica is a close resemblance to *Gridhrasi* based on its aetiology & symptomatology. Sciatica is a clinical condition characterized by radicular

pain beginning from the low back region and radiating downward along the course of the sciatic nerve. It can occur with or without lower extremity pain unilaterally or bilaterally, which may cause neurological deficits, including muscle weakness, absence of tendon reflexes or sensory deficit, numbness, and bladder dysfunction in some cases. It is a condition caused by sciatic nerve root (L4-S3) compression caused by vertebral disc protrusion or prolapse. Treatment options include pharmacological and non-pharmacological options. However, pain-relieving medications, such as NSAIDs have uncertain

benefits and might have adverse effects.^[3] This case was treated with Ayurvedic therapeutic interventions such as *Kati basti*, *Sthanika abhyanga* and *Sweda*, *Matra basti* and *Marma* massage along with *Vatakaphahara* and *Vatahara shamana aushadhi* which gave significant improvement in symptoms and quality of life.

CASE REPORT

A 34-year-old male, employed as a painter, belonging to middle economic class, with no known history of any co-morbidities came to the OPD of Sri Paripoorna Sanathana Ayurveda Medical Hospital, Bengaluru with complaints of pain & stiffness in the lower back since 6 months associated with radiating pain in B/L lower limbs up to thighs. He also complains of distension of abdomen and occasional constipation since 1 year.

Patient gives a history of pain which started gradually during his painting work and aggravated on lifting heavy

things and strenuous work. Pain was continuous and progressive in nature. Pain used to relieve temporarily on rest or hot compression. For these complaints, the patient had consulted various local clinics and was being treated with analgesics when consulted, this helped relieve his pain temporarily. On continuing his work, pain used to worsen. Hence, for the above complaints, the patient has now approached Sri Paripoorna Sanathana Ayurveda Medical Hospital, Bengaluru for better management and care.

Clinical Findings

Clinical examinations pertaining to lumbar spine and hip joints were performed. Hip joint examinations were normal. Lumbar spine examination revealed local tenderness at the level of L4-L5, L5-S1. The range of movements was painful and restricted. Details of clinical findings are described in Table 1.

Range of movements:	Results:	
Flexion	Possible with pain, mild restriction	
Extension	Possible with pain, moderate restriction	
	Right	Left
SLR test	+ve at 30 degree	+ve at 60 degree
Lasegue test	+ve	+ve

Sciatica Bothersome Index

Not
Bothersome

Somewhat
Bothersome

Extremely
Bothersome

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Leg Pain						5	
Numbness or tingling in the foot or groin				3			
Weakness in the leg or foot		1					
Back or leg pain while sitting						5	

SBI Total- 14

Investigations

MRI Lumbosacral Spine: Impression dated 06/01/2025.

- At L4-L5 disc level, diffuse circumferential disc buldge insignificantly indenting in thecal sac.
- Early spondylo-degenerative changes in whole spine

Management & Outcome

The Ayurvedic treatment was administered in the form of *Kati basti*, *Sthanika abhyanga* & *Sweda*, *Matra basti* and *Marma* massage. *Shamana aushadhi* were also administered during the course of treatment in the hospital. The therapeutic interventions and their timelines are described in Table 2.

Date	Treatment	Details
11/07/2025 to 16/07/2025	<i>Kati Basti</i>	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i>
11/07/2025 to 15/07/2025	<i>Sthanika Abhyanga</i> followed by <i>Nadi sweda</i>	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i>
12/07/2024 to 16/07/2025	<i>Matra basti</i>	<i>Sahacharadi Taila</i>
16/09/2025-17/09/2025	<i>Sthanika Marma massage</i> followed by <i>Nadi sweda</i>	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i>
Oral Medications		
	Tablet Spynovin 1-0-1 After food	
2.	Tablet <i>Kamadugha Vati</i> 1-0-1 Before food	
3.	<i>Hingwashtaka Choorna</i> 1/2tsp+Ghee with first bolus of food BD	

The details and dosages of medication advised on discharge are described in Table 3.

1. Tablet Spynovin 1-0-1 After food
2. <i>Hingwashtaka Choorna</i> 1/2tsp+Ghee with first bolus of food BD
3. <i>Gandharvahasthadi Eranda Taila</i> 0-0-1/2tsp with warm water After food at bed time

The outcomes were measured with evaluation of range of movements as described in Table 4. Significant improvement was seen in clinical outcomes with respect

to Range of Movements after completion of therapeutic intervention. Complaints of distension of the abdomen were also improved.

Table 4.

Range of movements:	Results	
Flexion	Possible without pain, no restriction	
Extension	Possible without pain, no restriction	
	Right	Left
SLR test	+ve at 80 degree	-ve
Lasegue test	-ve	-ve

Sciatica Bothersome Index

Not
Bothersome

Somewhat
Bothersome

Extremely
Bothersome

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Leg Pain		1					
Numbness or tingling in the foot or groin		1					
Weakness in the leg or foot		1					
Back or leg pain while sitting		1					

SBI Total- 4

DISCUSSION

Discussion about disease

Gridhrasi is a disease mainly caused due to *Vata dosha prakopa*^[4], which leads to degenerative changes. *Vata* is responsible for movements of the body^[5] which also correlates to the actions of the nervous system, when this is aggravated, it results in diseases which hamper the above functions. Similarly, in sciatica, the sciatic nerve is affected which results in radiating pain along the nerve root. Mainly *Vyana vata* is said to be affected. Along with *Vyana vata*, *Apana vata* may also be involved due to its *Sthana* and *karma*.^[6] Similarly, in *Gridhrasi*, due to *dhatu kshaya* i.e., degenerative changes of the spine and due to *avarana* i.e., traumatic or acute or immunological changes of the spine, it results in *stambha* and *ruja* in the *kati* and *adhoshakha* along the route of sciatic nerve. This typically presents with pain in the lower back radiating to lower limbs.

Discussion about treatment-

According to the treatment principles, *Vata vyadhi* should be managed with procedures like *Snehana*, *Swedana* and *Basti*.^[7] *Snehana* helps in combating the *rukshata*^[8] caused due to degenerative changes or due to over-use, *Swedana* helps in reducing *shoola* and *sthambha*^[9] caused due to radiating nervine pain and adjacent muscle spasms and *Basti* helps in overall balancing on *Vata dosha*. Hence, in this case, *Bahya snehana* was done with *kati basti* and *sthanika abhyanga* using *Mahanarayana taila*, by the virtue of its *vatahara* action, this may help reduce localised pain and nourish the localised *dhatu* by its *snehana* action. *Swedana* with

nadi sweda was done using *Dashamoola kwatha* which has *shothahara* action.^[10], which reduces the localised inflammation. *Matra basti* with *Sahacharadi taila* was done for its *Vatahara* action mainly targeting the *Vyana vata* and correcting the neuro-muscular pathology. Marma points are specific areas on the body which has relation to various internal organs, doshas, and strotas. Marma points can be used to balance the tridoshas and trigunas. During marma therapy, an extremely light stimulation of points on the body is applied by hand. This gets rid of the obstruction from that vital point. Instant pain relief is the motive of marma therapy. Stimulation of marma can produce an analgesia effect.^[11] Marma massage was done in this case with *Mahanarayana taila*. *Shamana aushadhi* with *Vatahara* property were prescribed. For G.I symptoms like Abdominal distention, Oral medications were prescribed having *Vata anulomana* action. This can help with both G.I symptoms as well as pain symptoms, as *Prakupita vata* moves in other directions during the stage of *Prasara* and cause *Sthana samshraya* in places with *khavaigunya*, hence, *Vata anulomana* helps correct the *Vata gati* and ultimately helps with *Shamana* of *Vata*.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic therapeutic interventions along with oral medicines were beneficial in improvement of the symptoms in *Ghridhrasi*. The results obtained from the treatment show that this treatment protocol can be used for successful treatment of *Ghridhrasi*.

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